

PREVALENCE OF NECK AND SHOULDER PAIN AMONG SCHOOL GOING CHILDREN WHO CARRY HEAVY BAG PACKS IN MODERN PUBLIC SCHOOL IN ABBOTTABAD.

Farhan Badshah¹, Rubi Nosheen², Shereen ZakaUllah³, Nasar Khan⁴, Iqra Iqbal⁵, Hira Naz⁶, Arif Shah⁷, Manzoor⁸

¹Physical Therapist Ali Medical Centre F8 Markaz Islamabad

²Physical Therapist, Aghaaz Rehabilitation Center

³Physical Therapist Alghazi Surgical & General Hospital Haripur

⁴Physical Therapist, Zamzum Autism Center E11 Islamabad

⁵Physical Therapist Taiba care Madina

⁶Physical Therapist & Lecturer Frontier Medical Institute Abbottabad.

⁷Physical Therapist Paraplegic Center Peshawar

⁸Physical Therapist Islamabad Club, Islamabad, Pakistan

¹Faranbadshah30@gmail.com, ²rubinosheen81@gmail.com, ³zsheen6@gmail.com,

⁴nasarkhan12922@gmail.com, ⁵iqraiqbal734@gmail.com, ⁶drnazjadoon@gmail.com,

⁷arifkmu90@yahoo.com, ⁸manzoorayaz68@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Arif Shah

Abstract

BACKGROUND: Children carry heavy school bags on daily bases and these loaded bags might cause serious pain in their neck and shoulder. The aim of this study is to find the prevalence of neck and shoulder pain due to school backpacks usage among students of Modern School System Abbottabad.

METHODOLOGY: The study included 120 students of modern school system aged between 10 to 15 years. A descriptive cross-sectional design was chosen. Data were collected using simple English language questionnaire.

RESULTS: The prevalence of students experience neck and shoulder pain ever during holding bag packs is 87 (72.5%). Students of 12-year-old were more prone to pain and frequency is 42(26%). Female student (88.8%) more pain than male student (62%6). Underweight student experiences 100%. Carrying bag on one shoulder cause more pain (63.33). Carrying bag for longer time cause more pain in neck and shoulder. Moderate pain is more experience by students and prevalence is 35.00.

CONCLUSION: Prevalence of neck and shoulder pain in teenagers is high due to carrying heavy schoolbag. Age, gender, manner of carrying backpacks, BMI, time for carrying bags is important factor in this study. Females are more prone to the neck and shoulder ache than males. Students under the age of 12 years are suffering from pain. In Addition, this work also provides evidence of carrying bag on one shoulder cause more pain than carrying bag on both shoulder

INTRODUCTION

Neck pain (NP) is likewise called cervical ache or cervicalgia [1]. Children and teenagers who are going to school are seriously affected by neck ache [2]. School going children brought high weight in school bags. Long time carrying of heavy school bags badly affect the growth of bones and cause stress in neck and shoulders. Heavy bags shifts the center of gravity of school child in the direction of weight [3]. The body posture and the musculoskeletal system compensate the stress that impose by heavy bags [4]. Carrying a heavy bags can result in a variety of pains, including musculoskeletal illnesses and postural dysfunctions [5]. According to the American Academy of Orthopaedic Surgeons (AAOS), Consumer Safety Commission (CSC) the number of children aged 5 to 18 seeking medical attention for back and shoulder pain connected to the use of heavy backpacks [6]. In order to minimize this problem of musculoskeletal pain, a recommended weight for school bag is limit to 10-15 % of body weight of child [7].

The main causes of neck and shoulder pain in students include heavy backpacks [8], the approach of carrying school bags [9], the interval of carrying bags [10], physical competency and movement with psychological aspects [11], school furniture [12], unsuitable posture [13], and congenital difficulties [14]. Risk factors include overweight backpacks [15], manner of carrying bags [16], prolonged use of heavy bags [10], physical inactivity, demographic illnesses [12], increased homework and curricula load [7], bag ergonomics [2], age and gender [10].

The prevalence of neck pain due to school bag use was reported as 56.6% among students in Lahore, Pakistan, while Ibrahim et al. (2015) in India found 48.6% [2]. Monthly prevalence was 35.8% for neck pain and 30.9% for shoulder pain [17]. Another study reported neck pain in 43.8% and shoulder pain in 93.8% of students [4]. Overall, 77.1% of students experienced musculoskeletal problems, mainly in the neck, shoulder, upper and lower back [7]. Prevalence was also higher in CBSE schools (73%) compared to SSC schools (55%), with English

medium schools reporting 77.4% and Marathi medium 36.9% [7].

This study will helpful in raising awareness regarding the effects of heavy bag packs on neck and shoulder thus help in developing preventive strategies of carrying school bags. Awareness about musculoskeletal problems can be raised with the help of teachers, policy makers and health care professionals by regular preventive and campaigns. Parents also play important role to prevent their children from such conditions.

Methods

This study used a descriptive cross-sectional design to determine the prevalence of neck and shoulder pain due to the use of school bags among students. Data were collected over six months at the Modern School System. The study population consisted of 172 students from classes 5th to 8th, with a final sample size of 120 participants. Ethical approval was obtained from the Advanced Study & Research Committee (ASRC) of FIMS College of Physical Therapy and Medical Rehabilitation. Informed consent was secured from students prior to data collection.

A non-probability convenience sampling technique was used, selecting students who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria included school-going students of classes 5th to 8th, carrying bags on one or both shoulders, and both male and female students. Exclusion criteria included pathological orthopedic or genetic causes of musculoskeletal symptoms, metabolic or neoplastic disorders, and any systemic disease-causing musculoskeletal problems.

For data collection, a self-administered questionnaire in simple English was used. After obtaining consent, students were asked to fill out the questionnaire, and demographic information was also recorded. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 16, and results were presented in frequency tables and percentages.

Ethical considerations included ensuring confidentiality of participants' information, informing students about the objectives of the

study, and clarifying that participation was voluntary and they could withdraw at any stage without consequences. Participants were also assured that the research carried no risk or harm.

Result

According to analysis the results showed that n=9(7.5%) were 10 year n= 29(24.2%) were 11 year ,n=42(35.0)were 12year, n=18(15.0) were

13year,n=14(11.7) were 14 year, n=8(6.7) were 15year,out of 120 participants. According to analysis the result show that n= 75(62.5) were male and n=45(37.5) were female out of 120 participants students. The data was analysis show that n=5(4.2%) have underweight, n=100(83.3%) have normal weight, n=13(10.8%) have overweight , n=2(1,7%) have obese out of 120.(table 1)

Table 1: Age, Gender, BMI

age of research participants		gender of research participants		BMI	
Year	Frequency		Frequency		frequency
10	9	Male	75	underweight	5
11	29			normal	100
12	42			overweight	13
13	18	Female	45	Obese	2
14	14			tatal	120
15	8				

The data was analysis show that n=87(72.5%), have a shoulder and neck pain and n=33(27.5%) not have a pain in shoulder and

neck during or after carrying your school bags out of 120 participants students. (table 2)

Table 2: experience pain in your shoulder/neck during or after carrying your school bags

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	87	72.5	72.5	72.5
	No	33	27.5	27.5	100.0
	Total	120	100.0	100.0	

The data analysis show the result n=1(8%) have 0 rate, n=39(32.5%) have 1-3 rate n=50(41.7%) have 4-6 rate, n=30(25.0%) have 7-6 rate of pain Rate your pain due to school bag out of 120 participants.(table 3)

Table 3: Rate your pain due to school bag

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0	1	.8	.8	.8
	1-3	39	32.5	32.5	33.3
	4-6	50	41.7	41.7	75.0
	7-10	30	25.0	25.0	100.0
	Total	120	100.0	100.0	

Discussion:

The main focus of a study was to inquire the prevalence of neck/shoulder pain among modern school system who carry heavy bag. A descriptive cross-sectional survey and the study duration of the current research is 6 months. The sample size is 120, which is calculated in Raosoft calculator. The results of this study showed that female students feel more pain in neck and shoulder than male. The frequency of pain in female students is 40 (88.8%) and in male students is 47 (62.6%). Female students have weak muscles and other study shows the results of a study which was carried by Amjid et al. which found female experience more pain than boys because female students have weak muscles and bones than males. The study is conducted in Lahore, Pakistan [1]. According to the results, the normal weight students experience more pain and frequency than obese, underweight and overweight and the other study report by Dianat et al. in their study gives the relationship between body weight and rate of pain due to carrying heavy school bags. The results indicate that the students of normal body weight experience more pain than the others. [14]. The results of this study show that most of the students ever experience pain in neck and shoulder during carrying bag packs. The frequency of students to feel pain ever during holding bags is 87 (72.5%). According to other study of students suffer from the neck (29.6%) and shoulder pain (44.4%) [17].

The majority of students carry bags on both shoulders and their frequency is 99 (82.5%). Out of total, 77 (77.7%) suffer from neck and shoulder pain. Only 21 (17.5%) of children

hold bags on one shoulder and 10 (47.6%) feel pain. Other study indicates that the students who carry bags on one shoulder experience more pain than the students who carry on two shoulders. [18]

The rate of pain is a key aspect of this research work. According to the data obtained from survey, only 1 (0.8%) of the total students feel no pain. 50 (41.7%) students experience moderate pain and rate is 4-6. Mild pain appears in 39 (32.5%) and severe pain condition in 30 (25%) students.

Conclusion:

This study concluded high prevalence of neck and shoulder pain in teenagers due to carrying of heavy schoolbags. Females are more prone to the neck and shoulder ache than males. Students under age of 12 years are suffering from pain. In addition, this work also provides evidence that the way of holding bags also causes the pain. In both cases, students suffer from pain but a student who carries bag on both shoulders feels more pain than who holds on single shoulder. Students having normal body weight experience more pain than others. Holding of bags for longer time also contributes to cervical and shoulder pain.

Limitations:

There are several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. Firstly, students were not properly participated in this study, which may have impacted the results. Secondly, the school management did not facilitate us during this study, potentially limiting the scope of the research. Additionally, the shortage of time was another major

limitation during this work. Furthermore, the limited resources constrained the scope of the study. Lastly, we did not take a detail of other clinical factors which are also the cause of pain, which could have provided a more comprehensive understanding of the issue.

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